

Forensic Use of Scientific and Physical Evidence in Bangladesh

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Abstract

The scheme of the law of evidence is to provide for the procedure of proof or disproof of a fact to ensure justice which is the aftermath of a proper and prompt investigation and trial based on both legal and scientific evidence. It is a great challenge, however, to utilise the scientific and physical evidence in administration of justice in our country due to shortcomings in the existing laws as well as the traditional attitude of our judicial mechanism to give more emphasis on ocular evidence. The want of an institutional mechanism establishing a nexus among police who are solely responsible for the task of investigation of an offence, judges through the prosecution, lawyers and forensic experts adds another impediment to the use of forensic evidence in aid of justice. This article is a modest attempt to depict the real scenario of how effectively the principles and norms of the forensic science are used in Bangladesh to administer justice as well as the major challenges the law enforcing agencies, lawyers and judges are facing in dealing with the scientific and physical evidence and the way out to overcome those.

Keywords: *Forensics, physical evidence, autopsy, CODIS, AFIS.*

Introduction

Administration of justice in a criminal case is a science that involves investigation and inquiry into the disputed matters, study of facts, identification of the offenders, location and

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proof of the guilt, collection and examination of the evidences to ensure punishments. With the tremendous advancement and easy accessibility to, the modern science and technology, the nature as well as the manner of commission of the crimes is frequently changing which requires highly sophisticated techniques to be employed in both investigation and trial stages. Of the various techniques employed by the modern-day investigations either in criminal or civil matters, scientific and physical evidences play the most decisive role in resolving a case or suit. However, unlike the other countries, lawyers, investigation officers and even judges of our country are hardly skilled enough to utilise these evidences for purposes of justice. Moreover, there is scarcity of both legal and infrastructural mechanisms as well as skilled manpower to collect, examine and preserve the physical evidences.

Considering the huge number of cases pending before the courts and very poor conviction rate, a strong legal framework ensuring forensic use of scientific and physical evidence is imperative. It will accelerate the investigation procedure that takes a longer period now and ultimately the conviction rate will augment to a great extent. An endeavour has been made in this outset to examine the existing laws of Bangladesh dealing with the admissibility and utility of the scientific and physical evidences in administration of justice with a view to pinpointing the shortcomings therein so that a justification can be raised to formulate a legal framework involving forensic experts, physicians, lawyers, judges and police to ensure public well-being and a high standard of justice.

Forensic Science

Forensic science is the application of science to those criminal and civil laws that are enforced by police agencies in a criminal justice system.¹ However, civil laws are not enforced by police in Bangladesh. The word ‘forensic’ derives from the Latin term ‘forensis’ which means ‘of or before the forum’.² In Roman times, a criminal charge meant presenting the case before a group of public individuals in the forum.³ Both the person accused of the

¹R. Saferstein, *Criminalistics An Introduction to Forensic Science*, (Englewood Cliffs, N.J.: Prentice Hall, Inc., 1990).

² *Shorter Oxford English Dictionary* (UK: Oxford University Press, 2007).

³ Michael Grant, *the Roman Forum*, (London: Weidenfeld & Nicolson; 1970).

crime and the accuser would give speeches based on their sides of the story. The individual with the best argument and delivery would determine the outcome of the case. In modern use, the term 'forensic' is a synonym for 'legal' or 'related to courts'. In these sense, forensic science can be termed as 'legal science'. Forensic science is the scientific method of gathering and examining information about the past. This is especially important in law enforcement where forensics is done in relation to criminal or civil law. All the branches of science, e.g. physics, chemistry, anatomy, physiology, medicine, surgery, chemistry, physics, and botany lend their aid as necessity arises and in some cases all these branches of science are required to enable a court of law to arrive at a proper conclusion on a contested question affecting life or property. In fine, forensics is concerned with the recognition, identification, individualization and evaluation of physical evidence using the methods of the natural sciences in matters of legal significance.⁴

Scientific and Physical Evidence

All legal means which help to prove or disprove any matter in question is called evidence. In the legal sense, evidence means and includes all statements which the court permits or requires to be made before it by witnesses, in relation to matters of fact under inquiry and all documents produced for the inspection of the court.⁵ A careful scrutiny of the Evidence Act will discover three modes for proof or disproof of a fact before the court of law, i.e. oral evidence, documentary evidence and physical or scientific evidence. Though the Act defines very exhaustively the oral and documentary evidences but physical or scientific evidence has not been defined.

Scientific Evidence

The phrase "scientific evidence" has become part of the vernacular in modern day administration of justice. Scientific evidence is information gathered from scientific research, which takes a lot of time and patience to conduct. From the legal point of view, scientific

⁴P.R. DeForest et al., *Forensic Science An Introduction to Criminalistics*, (New York: McGraw Hill, Inc. 1983).

⁵The Evidence Act, 1872, s. 3.

evidence is a kind of evidence derived from scientific knowledge or techniques. For instance, most of the forensic evidence including genetic evidence is scientific evidence. Section 45 of the Evidence Act recognised the scientific evidence as relevant⁶ though the Act provides no further provisions determining the standard of its admissibility to courts. However, to be admissible, the expert who conducts the experiment in the laboratory must appear before the court and be undergone examinations as an ordinary witness.⁷ In addition, qualification of the experts as well as the validity of the scientific theory used must be generally accepted. Most jurisdictions require the theory used by an expert witness to meet certain qualifications before being used in court. The two most common are the Daubert and Frye tests.⁸

The Frye standard otherwise known as general acceptance test is a test to determine the admissibility of scientific evidence.⁹ It provides that expert opinion based on a scientific technique is admissible only where the technique is generally accepted as reliable in the relevant scientific community. While Daubert Test requires four things to be shown, i.e. (i) that the theory is testable, (ii) that the theory has been peer reviewed as the same will usually reduce the chances of error in the theory, (iii) that the reliability and error rate though 100% reliability and zero error are not required, but the rates should be considered by the trial judge and (iv) that the extent of general acceptance by the scientific community.¹⁰

For instance, the Formaldehyde Metre Z-300, a kit used in Bangladesh for detecting formalin in food since 2012 has recently been challenged as unfit and inappropriate scientific device in a writ petition filed by the Fruit Importers' Association.¹¹ Following the writ petition, the High Court Division asked the government on July 21 to have the machine checked by

⁶ The Evidence Act, s. 45.

⁷ See sections 60 & 137 of the Evidence Act, 1872.

⁸ Sheila Jasanoff, *Science at the Bar: Law, Science, and Technology in America* (Cambridge, Mass.: Harvard University Press, 1997) 214.

⁹ *Frye vs. United States*, 293 F. 1013 (D.C... Cir 1923).

¹⁰ *Daubert v. Merrell Dow Pharmaceuticals*, 509 U.S. 579 (1993).

¹¹ The petition was filed in the wake of widespread protests from fruit traders against the destruction of tones of fruits, by the Dhaka Metropolitan Police early June, 2014. The DMP in its three-week-drive used the Formaldehyde Metre imported by the Department of Fisheries (DoF) from the US manufacturer, Environmental Sensors Co, in early 2012. It bought 80 devices at a cost of Tk. 1 crore and distributed those in every division and district for mobile court drives.

Bangladesh Standards and Testing Institution (BSTI), BCSIR and National Food Safety Laboratory (NFSL) and submit separate reports in four weeks. The High Court Division, on receiving the report of BCSIR, declared the Formaldehyde Metre Z-300 as inappropriate and ordered the Government to constitute an expert committee for procuring detectors suitable for tracing formalin in food.¹²

The scientific and physical evidence is given utmost priority by the judiciary of Bangladesh. In the case of *Tarak Chandra Majhi vs. Atahar Ali Howladar*,¹³ it was held by the Appellate Division that the safe and best course for the court would be to avoid the practice of comparing the writing or signature ... and the desired course should be to go for microscopic enlargement and expert advice since the science of examination of similarity has advanced enough and it has reached to the stage of accuracy and certainty as well as expertise skill is also available. However, the court is found to be very much careful regarding the standard and authenticity of scientific evidence as it was held in *Rahimuddin vs. the State*¹⁴ that identification by finger-prints stands, however, on a safer footing where the expert is found sufficiently trained and qualified in the science.

Physical Evidence

Physical evidence refers to any material object that plays some actual role in the matter that gave rise to the litigation, introduced in a trial, intended to prove a fact in issue based on its demonstrable physical characteristics.¹⁵ Physical evidence can conceivably include all or part of any object. Physical evidence usually involves objects found at the scene of a crime.¹⁶ Also referred to as real evidence, physical evidence consists of tangible articles such as hairs, fibers, latent fingerprints, footprints and handprints, glove prints, tidemarks, cut marks, impression evidence – shoe prints, tire tracks or tool marks, biological materials – DNA,

¹²<http://www.bdnews24.com/bangladesh/2014/11/24/get-formalin-detectors-for-food-hc>, retrieved on 10.12.2014.

¹³ 8 BLC (AD) 67.

¹⁴ 12 DLR (1960) 453.

¹⁵ Elizabeth A. Martin, *A Dictionary of Law*, (UK: Oxford University Press, 2009) 30.

¹⁶ The USLegal Dictionary <http://definitions.uslegal.com/p/physical-evidence/>.

blood, semen and saliva, fracture patterns – glass fragments or adhesive tape pieces, narcotics, firearms and so forth.

Like scientific evidence, no reference is found in the Evidence Act as to the physical evidence. The Draft Amendment of the Evidence Act defines physical evidence as any material or object (i) that may establish that an offence has been committed or may establish a link or relation between an offence and its victim or an offence and its offender; (ii) that may prove or disprove a fact such as blood, semen, hairs, all body materials, organs of parts of organs, Deoxyribonucleic Acid (DNA), finger impressions, palm impressions, foot prints, latent prints, photograph, traced print, reports originated from all automated identification systems, etc.¹⁷ This definition seems to be exhaustive.

Scientific and Physical Evidence in the Context of Bangladesh

The existing civil and criminal laws of Bangladesh leave an ample scope for a wide range of application of scientific and physical evidence in administration of justice. Though there are some in-built limitations and procedural shortcomings, the existing laws provide a guideline to apply the scientific and physical evidence not only in administration of civil and criminal justice but also in resolving other disputes regarding civil and human rights of the citizen.

Civil Laws

The scientific and physical evidence can be best utilised in determining genetic relationship or legitimacy of children,¹⁸ issues affecting the civil rights of the citizen which includes, *inter alia*, physical and mental competency to enter into a contract,¹⁹ physical fitness for public job, determination of age, etc., medical assessment of injuries to persons²⁰, settlement of immigration disputes,²¹ the ethical duty of the physicians, testamentary disposition and so

¹⁷ The Draft Evidence (Amendment) Ordinance, 2007, s. 2. (This draft was prepared with the assistance of the UNDP in 2007. However, the Government did not make any move to cause it placed before the Parliament).

¹⁸ The Evidence Act, 1872, S. 112.

¹⁹ The Contract Act, Ss. 11 and 12.

²⁰ The Code of Civil Procedure, 1908, S. 19.

²¹ Sheikh Hafizur Rahman Karzon, "Interrelationship of Genetics and Criminal Behaviour: Challenges for Judges and Lawyers" *Dhaka University Law Journal, Studies Part-F*, Vol. 18, No. 1, (2007) 21.

forth. Moreover, scientific and physical evidence plays a vital role in examining various documents produced before the courts in civil litigation either by plaintiffs or defendants. Sometimes, it becomes necessary to identify a dead body and to ascertain medical cause of death for the settlement of insurance claims as well as payment of compensation in case of death in work place. For instance, the extremely decomposed bodies of some victims of Tazrin Fashions and Rana Plaza incidence were identified by matching the DNA samples collected from the bodies with those of their relatives. On April 28, 2013, a writ petition was filed at the High Court Division of the Supreme Court seeking arrest of the owner of Tazreen Fashions Limited for his ignorance. On June 8, 2013, the High Court Division directed the authority concerned to carry out the DNA tests of the families of 37 missing victims' of Tazreen Fashion fire so that the bereaved families could be compensated. Forensic engineers provide courts with necessary expertise in resolving disputes relating to the design and construction of buildings, fitness of vehicles and electronics and other items. Forensic linguists determine the authorship of written documents through analyses of handwriting, syntax, word usage and grammar. Scientific and physical evidence is also applicable in assessing the validity of a tape-recorded message, the identification of speakers of the recorded message and other aspects of electronic documents.²²

Criminal Laws

The scientific and physical evidence has enormous utility in administration of criminal justice in Bangladesh. In a rape case, for instance, physical evidence like DNA collected from inside the body of the victim is used to identify the culprit. In fact, some complex medico-legal issues can hardly be resolved without considering scientific and physical evidence. Scientific and physical evidence plays decisive roles in investigation into the crimes against the human body,²³ unnatural deaths,²⁴ insanity,²⁵ cyber crimes²⁶ and so forth.

²² According to section 87 of the Information and Communication Technology Act, 2006, any document produced electronically or with the assistance of technology is admissible as evidence.

²³ The Penal Code, 1860, Chapter 16.

²⁴ The Code of Criminal Procedure, 1898, Sections 174 and 176.

²⁵ As per section 84 of the Penal Code, 1860, an accused may plea a defence of unsoundness of mind to have exemption from criminal liability.

Crimes against the human body include bodily harm,²⁷ rape and other sexual assaults,²⁸ criminal abortion,²⁹ infanticide and homicide.³⁰ In investigation of these crimes, and in prosecution of the offenders, scientific and physical evidence plays a very significant role and the opinion of the forensic experts is very important for the court to come up with a reasonable decision.³¹

Scientific and physical evidence is also applicable in offences relating to counterfeiting currencies and government stamps, offences affecting public health, e.g. adulteration of drug and food.³² Recently the Pure Food Act, 2013 has been enacted in the Parliament which has created the scope to use still photographs and video records of food adulteration as evidence before the courts. Moreover, in determining whether adulterants have been mixed in a food item, the court will have to consider the scientific report of the designated laboratory.³³

Utility of Scientific and Physical Evidence

The examination of physical evidence by a forensic investigator is usually undertaken for identification and comparison. A fact can be proved or disproved either by oral testimony or by documentary evidence or by physical evidence. According to Dr. Locard, the evolution of the burden of proof underwent four main steps namely providence – ordeals or combats, confession, witness' testimony and physical evidence. He believed that when a criminal came into contact with an object or person, a cross transfer of evidence occurs.³⁴

The distinctive characteristic of physical or scientific evidence is that it tells a story and helps an investigator recreate the crime scene and establish the sequence of events. Physical evidence can corroborate statements from the victims, witnesses and/or suspects. If analyzed and interpreted properly, physical evidence is more reliable than testimonial evidence.

²⁶ Pornography Control Act, 2012, the Information and Communication Technology Act, 2006.

²⁷ The Penal Code, 1860, S. 319.

²⁸ See section 375 of the Penal Code, 1860 and sections 9, 11 and 13 of the Prevention of Women and Children Repression Act, 2000.

²⁹ The Penal Code, 1860, S. 316.

³⁰ The Penal Code, 1860, Ss. 299, 300 and 302.

³¹ The Evidence Act, 1872, S. 45.

³² The Penal Code, 1860, Chapters 12 and 14.

³³ The Pure Food Act, 2013, Ss. 72 and 73.

³⁴ R. Saferstein, *Criminalistics*, 22.

Testimonial evidence is more subjective in nature because an individual's perception of events and memory of what happened can be incomplete or inaccurate. Physical evidence, on the other hand, is objective and when documented, collected and preserved properly may be the only way to reliably place or link someone with a crime scene. Physical evidence is therefore often referred to as the 'silent witness.' Moreover, a witness may tell a lie or may be biased while deposing his testimony before the courts but physical evidence will never tell a lie. With the passage of time, oral testimony will certainly damage or become unavailable but decade old physical evidence can be used in evidence. Though there is no certainty that oral testimony or other documentary evidences will be available at every crime scene, there must be physical evidence following every crime as the *Locard's Exchange Principle* states that:

Wherever he steps, whatever he touches, whatever he leaves—even unconsciously—will serve as silent evidence against him. Not only his fingerprints or his shoeprints, but also his hair, the fibers from his clothes, the glass he breaks, the tool mark he leaves, the paint he scratches, the blood or semen that he deposits or collects -- all these and more bear mute witness against him. This is evidence that does not forget. It is not confused by the excitement of the moment. It is not absent but human witnesses are. It is factual evidence. Physical evidence cannot be wrong; it cannot perjure itself; it cannot wholly be absent. Only in its interpretation can there be error. Only human failure to find, study, and understand it can diminish its value.³⁵

Evidential Value of Scientific and Physical Evidence

According to section 45 of the Evidence Act, scientific evidence as expert opinion is relevant fact before the courts. That is to say such evidence is merely expert opinion, not a substantive piece of evidence because relevancy does not mean admissibility. So far the admissibility of the physical evidence is concerned, a new section was purported to be inserted in the Evidence Act which provides that when the court has to form an opinion as to whom the physical evidence relates to, the opinions upon the identity of such physical evidence of persons specially skilled in identifying and verifying such physical evidence are relevant.³⁶ Again, to make such evidence relevant, the requirement of section 60 of the Evidence Act shall be fulfilled. The section requires that oral evidence must, in all cases, be direct, that is, if

³⁵ P.L. Kirk, *Crime Investigation*, (New York: John Wiley & Sons, Inc., 1974) 30.

³⁶ The Draft Evidence (Amendment) Act, 2007, s. 47A.

it refers to an opinion or to the grounds on which that opinion is held, it must be the evidence of the person who holds that opinion on those grounds. Section 60 of the Evidence Act makes it very clear that the evidence of such an opinion must be the evidence of a person who holds that opinion and he should be examined as a witness in the case.³⁷

In the case of *Abdul Quddus vs. The State*³⁸ his Lordship Latifur Rahman, J. held that medical evidence is only corroborative in nature. However, the expert opinion is not binding upon the court as it was held in the case of *Prafulla Kamal Bhattacharya vs. Ministry of Home Affairs, Govt. of Bangladesh*³⁹ that section 45 of the Evidence Act provides that the opinion of an expert on a point of foreign law or science or art coming for determination before a court, is relevant. This section does not say that the opinion of an expert is binding upon the court.

Procedure of Depositing Scientific and Physical Evidence to Courts

The scientific and physical evidence comes through the research conducted by the scientists or experiments and comparisons undertaken by the forensic experts like physicians, chemists, serologists, ballistics experts, etc. in the laboratory. In fact, scientific and physical evidence includes a scientific theory, language of machines, digital video, recording as well as opinion or assistance of the concerned experts like Information Technology experts.⁴⁰ Therefore, this evidence cannot be deposited to courts in an ordinary way; rather a special procedure is to be followed in this regard as the Supreme Court of India held in the case of *State of Maharashtra vs. Gopinath Shinde and others*⁴¹ that without examining the expert as a witness in court, no reliance can be placed on an opinion alone. Similarly, in *Usman Khan vs. State*⁴² his Lordship Muhammad Yakub Ali, J. observed that...judges are not experts in medical science to form a safe opinion on these matters. It is desirable therefore...to summon the doctor who examined the injuries or performed the autopsy as a witness and investigate the reasons for his opinion.

The concerned forensic expert is served with summon to appear before the court on a fixed date for testifying. He is testified like a general witness, that is, he steps in the witness-box and has to

³⁷ Kutubuddin Ahmed Siddiky vs. East Pakistan Industrial Development Corporation, 27 DLR 433.

³⁸ 43 DLR AD (1991) 234.

³⁹ 28 DLR (1976)123.

⁴⁰ See the Pornography Control Act, 2012, s. 7.

⁴¹ AIR (2000) SC 1691.

⁴² 21 DLR SC (1969) 194.

take the oath before he starts his deposition. Before examination, the relevant documents, e.g. post-mortem report or any other scientific reports are submitted to the court. Then the forensic expert is examined which consists of examination in chief, cross examination and re-examination.⁴³ In the examination in chief, the medical expert states all the facts within his knowledge concerning the case. The examination of the concerned expert is very important as his interpretation of the facts laid down in the forensic reports bear much more value. In the case of *Hadiuzzaman vs. The State*⁴⁴ it was held that the deposition made by the medical officer on oath is a substantive piece of evidence, whereas his medical certificate is a corroboration of his evidence on oath. However, the law has provided some exceptional circumstances under which the court may dispense with the examination of the concerned expert.⁴⁵ It was argued in a case before the High Court Division that non-examination of the Chemical examiner who was a charge sheeted witness was fatal and shall give rise to presumption under section 114(g) of the Evidence Act but the Court did not accept this argument and held the view that under section 510 of the Code, the report could be used in evidence without calling the chemical examiner.⁴⁶

The Information & Communication Technology Act, 2006 or Evidence Act, 1872, does not provide sufficient guideline for the use of ‘language of machine or recording’ in evidence. Tape recordings, video cassette, snapshot of hand cameras, photographs as well as languages of machine like the hard-disks installed within computers, the removable floppy disks, CDs and DVD’s used for temporary storage fall within the definition of documentary evidence.⁴⁷ All computer-generated and electronically produced evidence are admissible as primary evidence.⁴⁸ However, the following requirements must be fulfilled while depositing such evidence to courts, i.e. (a) chain of custody/ continuity of evidence; (b) transparent forensic procedures; (c) accuracy of process; (d) accuracy of content; (e) explanations.⁴⁹

⁴³The Evidence Act, 1972, s. 137.

⁴⁴BLD, AD (1986) 191.

⁴⁵The Code of Criminal Procedure, 1898, Ss. 509A & 510; see also 7 BLT (AD) 337, 5 BLC (AD) 41.

⁴⁶12 BLC 553.

⁴⁷ The Evidence Act, 1872, S. 3 and The Information and Communication Technology Act, 2006, S. 87.

⁴⁸ Mrs. Khaleda Akter v. the State, 37 DLR (1985) 275.

⁴⁹ Abu Hena Mostofa Kamal, “Integration of Forensic Techniques into the Threshold of Admissibility of Computer Derived Evidence: Should the Paradigm be Re-phrased?” *ASA University Review*, Vol. 5 No. 1, (2011) 37.

Legal Framework of Scientific and Physical Evidence in Bangladesh

Despite many shortcomings, the existing laws of our country leave an ample scope for a wide range of application of forensic science in both civil and criminal matters. The forensic experts can play a vital role in the process of investigation into crimes and help the investigation officer get final opinion as regards the nature of wounds in injury cases and time and cause of death, in cases where unnatural death has occurred. However, this is the demand of time that the centuries old legal framework dealing with the forensic use of scientific and physical evidences be amended otherwise some highly complex medico-legal issues can hardly be resolved. The laws dealing with scientific and physical evidence in Bangladesh are as follows:

- i. *Section 45 of Evidence Act, 1872*: It deals with forensic arts, fingerprinting and handwriting.
- ii. *Section 174 of Code of Criminal Procedure, 1898*: This provides the provisions of inquest investigation and autopsy which fall under the area of forensic pathology or forensic medicine.
- iii. *Section 176(2) of Code of Criminal Procedure, 1898*: This empowers the magistrates or trial courts to order for disinterment or exhumation of dead bodies from the grave that is the matter of forensic medicine.
- iv. *Section 510 of Code of Criminal Procedure, 1898*: It provides the court with discretion as to the admissibility of the reports of forensic chemical experts, ballistic experts and serologists appointed by the government without personal appearance.
- v. *Section 23 of the Prevention Women and Children Act, 2000*: Deals with admissibility of the evidence of physicians, chemical examiners, serologists, fingerprint experts, handwriting experts and ballistics experts.
- vi. *Section 48 of the Acid Control Act, 2002*: It requires the Government to establish chemical labs to analyse the category, amount and degree of the acid used in an offence.

- vii. *Sections 464 of Code of Criminal Procedure & 84 of Penal Code, 1860*: These prescribe the procedure of the trial of an insane person. Forensic psychology and psychiatry will come into aid of courts in this regard.
- viii. *Sections 6 & 7 of the Pornography Control Act, 2012 & 5(2) of the Information and Communication Technology Act, 2006*: These deal with digital forensics covering the area of computer forensics, forensic data analysis, database forensics, mobile device forensics, network forensics, forensic video, forensic audio.
- ix. *The DNA Act, 2014*: It deals with the provisions for collecting and testing of DNA samples as well establishment of National DNA Database.
- x. *Article 53 of the Constitution of the Peoples' Republic of Bangladesh*: This enumerates the provisions for the removal of the President on the ground of physical and mental incapacity.
- xi. *Articles 48, 66, 122 of the Constitution of the Peoples' Republic of Bangladesh*: These prescribe the minimum age to be the President, Member of Parliament and Voter respectively. Any dispute regarding the prescribed age is to be resolved with the assistance of scientific and physical evidence.
- xii. *Sections 11 and 12 of the Contract Act, 1872*: These provides, *inter alia*, the age of majority and sound mind as competency of a person to enter into a contract.
- xiii. *Section 3 of the Majority Act, 1875*: Determines 18 years as the age of adulthood of persons domiciled in Bangladesh.
- xiv. *Section 4 read with section 2 of the Child Marriage Restraint Act, 1929*: These fix the marriageable ages for males and females. In respect of marriage not only to identify age but also to identify relationship of bride and bridegroom like brother and sister, scientific or DNA test may be necessary.
- xv. *Section 19 of the Code of Civil Procedure, 1908*: It deals with suits for compensation for wrong to persons. Wrong caused to a person is a tortious liability which can be assessed by analyzing physical evidence and opinion of the concerned experts.
- xvi. *Sections 42 and 62 of the Consumers Rights Protection Act, 2009*: This deal with the procedure of collection and sending samples of food items to the laboratory to examine the presence of adulterants therein.

xvii. *The Pure Food Act, 2013*: Prescribes the procedure of using scientific reports in evidence as to whether any adulterant has been used in food.

The above legal framework suffers from a number of loopholes. Most of the provisions were enacted more than hundred years ago and have not been subjected to amendment to adopt the generally accepted scientific principles developed over the years. For instance, section 112 of the Evidence Act, 1872, deals with the conclusive proof of the legitimacy of a child born either within 280 days of the subsistence of marriage or after 280 days of the annulment of marriage provided the woman remains unmarried. Besides, the section provides the way of rebuttal of such presumption by adducing the proof of non-access between the alleged husband and wife during the aforesaid period. This section shall have no application to a case where the maternity of a person is in dispute and not his paternity.⁵⁰ Such provision has now been obsolete because it is time consuming and sometimes very difficult to adduce the proof of non-access. So DNA fingerprinting is the more appropriate means to come up with a reasonable conclusion.

There is lack of adjustment in the existing laws. For instance, the Information and Communication Technology Act brought about amendments to the following Acts in respect of documents.⁵¹ The definition of "document" in section 29 of Penal Code and section 3 of Evidence Act, also includes the document generated or prepared by electronic machine or technology; the definition of "bankers books" in section 2, Clause (3) of Banker's Books Evidence Act also includes the books viz. ledgers, day-books, cash-books, account-books and all other books generated or prepared by electronic machine or technology. But the respective laws have not been up to date accordingly.

Discrepancies are found in law and practice so far the post mortem of dead bodies is concerned. The legal provisions on post mortem examination are enshrined in section 174 of the Code of Criminal Procedure (CrPC) and regulations 303 to 308 of the Police Regulations of Bengal (PRB). According to law, the procedure of post mortem is preceded by an inquest

⁵⁰ M. Monir, *Law of Evidence*, (Allahabad: University Book Agency, 2004) p. 528.

⁵¹The Information and Communication Technology Act, 2006, S. 87.

investigation conducted by the officer in charge of the concerned police station. The police officer shall send the dead body for post-mortem examination to the nearest Civil Surgeon where there is any doubt regarding the cause of death, or when for any other reason the police-officer considers it expedient so to do. The dead body must be accompanied by a copy of inquest report and a *challan* in triplicate in B.P. Form No. 49. On completing the post-mortem examination, the medical officer shall prepare a report in the B.P. Form No. 50 and a copy thereof shall be forwarded to the Superintendent of Police who shall cause the same to be laid before the court concerned. In our country, medico-legal investigations lags behind the normal standard followed. In the cities where a government medical college is available any academic staff of forensic medicine department is empowered to perform an autopsy otherwise, by the civil surgeon in the district hospitals. However, in practice, reality is far from these words. It is seen in most of the district hospitals that untrained doctors from any branch are involved in the procedures of post mortem. They are not especially trained but chosen from other duties on a particular day.⁵² Therefore, they just sign the reports and the entire activities are performed by dooms. The post-mortem report helps the police officer come up with a reasonable conclusion as to the actual cause of death. Hence he will have to go through the report very carefully as each and every word of the report is very significant for the investigation into the cause and manner of death. Unfortunately, most of the investigation officers do hardly understand the post-mortem report as the same is written in the language of medical science.⁵³ As per regulation 306(b) of the PRB, police officers shall refer to the Civil Surgeon if they have any doubt in regard to any part of the medical report but the real scenario is totally different. Even the situation goes the worst when the post-mortem report does not contain the actual cause of death. As a result, thousands of deaths buried without proper investigation in Bangladesh. The age old practice of two finger test applied on rape victims was a great obstacle for the victims to get justice as in most of the cases the victims do not want to undergo a second rape in the name of medical test. Recently

⁵² Rahman KGM, Osman MK and Mahmud S, "Forensic Medicine: Bangladesh Perspective" *Journal of Dhaka Medical College*, Vol. 19, No. 1 (2010) 61.

⁵³ Kamrul Hasan, "Police does not understand language of autopsy," *Daily Prothom-alo*, April 20, 2012, sec. D.

in a writ petition, the High Court Division of the Supreme Court of Bangladesh has prohibited such an extremely violent, unscientific, inhuman and degrading ‘two finger test’ and directed the Government to formulate a guideline to be followed in examining rape victims.⁵⁴

Another hurdle to utilising the knowledge of forensic medicine is the admissibility of forensic evidence to the courts. As it is discussed earlier medical evidence under the existing laws of the country is merely expert opinion or secondary evidence, sometimes it becomes very difficult to corroborate such evidence to ensure conviction of the offenders.⁵⁵ Recently, the Parliament has enacted the Deoxyribonucleic Acid (DNA) Act, 2014 providing, *inter alia*, the admissibility of the DNA evidence to the courts as primary evidence.

Traditionally, our investigation and trial mechanisms give much more emphasis on confessional statements than the forensic evidence and this is very clear from the decision of the apex court. In several cases, the Appellate Division held the view that if the fact of causing injuries was proved by eye witnesses and if there was no reason to disbelieve their evidence, conviction could be given relying on the evidence of the eye witnesses even if the medical evidence did not support the prosecution case.⁵⁶

When medical or scientific or physical evidence will differ from eye witnesses or other documentary or direct evidences, benefit of doubt will go in favour of the accused which result in his acquittal. It is unsafe to rely upon the direct evidence of the eyewitnesses when it is in conflict with the medical evidence.⁵⁷ If the evidence of the witness for the prosecution is totally inconsistent with the medical evidence, it is a most fundamental defect in the prosecution case and unless reasonably explained, it is sufficient to discredit the entire case.⁵⁸ Such an awkward situation can easily be avoided by utilisation of forensic and scientific evidence.

For speedy investigation and trial, an efficient and integrative investigation mechanism is imperative. But the investigation agencies in Bangladesh are encountering many challenges

⁵⁴ See the Writ Petition No. 10663/2013 filed Bangladesh Legal Aid and Services Trust (BLAST) along with five leading NGOs, Ain O Salish Kendra, Bangladesh Mahila Parishad, BRAC, Manusher Jonno Foundation, Naripokkho and two medical experts, Dr. Ruchira Tabassum Naved of and Dr. Mobarak Hossain Khan.

⁵⁵ The Evidence Act, 1872, Ss. 45 & 60.

⁵⁶ 37 DLR AD (1985)113, see also 7BCR (AD) 78, 43 DLR AD (1991) 234.

⁵⁷ Md. Asrafur Islam, Afsar Uddin and Ahamuduzzaman, “Medical Evidence and Medical Witness” *ASA University Review*, Vol. 2, No. 1 (2008) 67.

⁵⁸ *Rahman vs. State of Punjab*, AIR (1975) SC 1727.

to flourish themselves as creative and independent institutions. These challenges are of two folds, i.e. shortcomings in the existing laws and lack of co-ordination among various disciplines concerned in the process of investigation of offences. The existing legal framework does not facilitate a separate investigation agency comprising of professionals and experts in different disciplines like police, forensic medicine experts, lawyers, ballistic experts and so forth.

As per the law, it is the sole responsibility of the police particularly in criminal matters to carry out the task of investigation for which they enjoy some powers as well.⁵⁹ But the police do not have sufficient number of trained manpower and logistic support to effectively and promptly discharge this function. Most of the officers concerned in the crime investigation do not understand the forensic reports because these reports like autopsy reports, injury certificates and burn reports are prepared in the language of medical science.⁶⁰ This problem of traditional investigation system may be overcome by introducing coroner investigation system or medical examination system particularly in inquest investigation. For instance, in the United States, the medico-legal investigation of unusual, suspicious, sudden and unexplained, violent, and non-natural deaths, including those deemed a possible threat to the public health, is usually performed by a coroner system or a medical examiner (ME) system.⁶¹

Present Scenario of AFIS and CODIS in Bangladesh

The existing laws do not provide sufficient guidelines as to the standards of collecting physical evidences including fingerprints and DNA from the crime scene. The Automated Fingerprint Identification System (AFIS) and Combined DNA Index System (CODIS) are very effective to promptly identify a person as well as link or eliminate a criminal to or from a crime. The country currently has one single laboratory at the Criminal Investigation Department (CID) which provides information on criminals' fingerprints but maintaining an electronic fingerprint database is still at an elementary stage. Recently Bangladesh Police under the Police Reform Programme

⁵⁹ See the Code of Criminal Procedure, 1898, Ss. 154-175.

⁶⁰ Kamrul Hasan, "Police does not understand language of autopsy," Daily Prothom-alo, April 20, 2012, sec. D.

⁶¹ R. Hanzlick and Combs D, *Medical examiner and coroner systems: history and trends* (JAMA: Mar, 1998) 870, <http://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pubmed/9516003>, retrieved on 10.11.2014.

(PRP) has taken an initiative to populate the Automated Fingerprint Identification System (AFIS). This initiative involves collecting approximately 67,000 fingerprints from convicted and remand prisoners in prisons throughout Bangladesh. The AFIS database population will increase the likelihood of investigators being able to match fingerprints found at crime scenes with fingerprints of previously incarcerated individuals.⁶² Law enforcement agencies have started to make use of the Election Commission's (EC) citizen database of more than 91.9 million citizens above the age of 18 to identify dead bodies and criminals by matching individuals' fingerprints. On August 19, officials at the city's Shah Ali police station sent the fingerprints from the dead body of an unidentified woman to the EC for identification. Using automated finger print identification (AFIS) software which matched her fingerprints with the EC reserved database, the EC managed to provide the woman's name and address and other information to the law enforcement agencies.⁶³ Such an effective method would bring changes in crime profiling, but there needs to be legal framework as to clarification on the procedure and its effect.

In Bangladesh, National Forensic DNA Profiling Laboratory was established at the forensic department of Dhaka Medical College Hospital in 2005 which has been given legal shape by the Deoxyribonucleic Acid (DNA) Act, 2014. It is an independent laboratory under the Ministry of Women and Children Affairs. The technology of DNA analysis and equipment used in this laboratory are claimed to be of international standard.⁶⁴ Moreover, sophisticated Combined DNA Index System (CODIS) software was added to this laboratory in 2013.⁶⁵ Now the great challenge is to train up the police, judges and lawyers on how to utilize DNA profile in civil and criminal proceedings.

Case Study on the Use of Forensic Evidence in Bangladesh

Determining Custody of the Seven Children

In 2006, reports were published in different newspapers about the ex-DIG couple claiming the parenthood of 14 children and seven of them appeared to be of the same. Bangladesh National

⁶² Annual Report, 2012: Ministry of Home Affairs, Government of the People's Republic of Bangladesh, Police Reform Programme (Phase II).

⁶³ Mohammad Zakaria, "Law enforcers to use EC's database to identify bodies" *The Dhaka Tribune*, August, 24, 2013, sec. Law & Rights.

⁶⁴ Sheikh Hafizur Rahman Karzon, "Interrelationship of Genetics and Criminal Behaviour: Challenges for Judges and Lawyers" *Dhaka University Law Journal, Studies Part-F*, Vol. 18, No. 1, (2007) 21.

⁶⁵ On September 25, 2013, the FBI donated this software to promptly identify 321 unidentified dead bodies of Savar's Rana Plaza Tragedy.

Women Lawyers' Association (BNWLA) and Bangladesh Society for the Enforcement of Human Rights (BSEHR) moved to the Chief Metropolitan Magistrate Court to conduct DNA tests of the couple and the children to verify their parenthood. When the court ordered to carry out the tests, the ex-DIG and his wife refused to cooperate. Later, Bangladesh National Women Lawyers' Association (BNWLA) and BSEHR filed a petition with the High Court, seeking permission for their DNA tests. On August 6, 2008, the HC asked the Dhaka Medical College authorities to carry out the tests under the supervision of the Supreme Court and ordered BNWLA and BSEHR to bear all expenses. Based on the DNA test reports, the HC on August 14 of that year ruled that the former DIG and his wife were not the biological parents of the septuplets. Then after the Fourth Special Tribunal for Prevention of Women and Children Repression, Dhaka sentenced Anisur Rahman and wife Anwara Rahman to 31 years rigorous imprisonment as the couple was found guilty of the crime.⁶⁶ Had the provision of section 112 of the Evidence Act been amended to include DNA test, such lengthy procedure could have been avoided.

Paracetamol Cases

Between 1990 and 1992, 339 children developed kidney failure, and most of them died, after being given paracetamol syrup contaminated with diethylene glycol. The outbreak forced the government to ban the sale of paracetamol elixirs in December 1992, causing a decline of 53% in the admission of patients with renal failure and an 84% decline in admissions by unexplained renal failure.⁶⁷ Actually, Bangladeshi hospitals first started seeing children with kidney failure in late 1982. But it took around ten years to establish that their deaths were due to taking paracetamol syrup containing diethylene glycol.

The prosecution filed cases against five pharmaceutical companies on December 19, 1992 when the Drug Testing Laboratory (DTL) with the direct supervision of a WHO consultant, examined the drugs samples of these companies and found the presence of toxic chemical diethylene glycol instead of propylene glycol in the syrup collected from these companies.⁶⁸

⁶⁶ Chaitanya Chandra Halder and Wasim Habib, "Ex-DIG, wife child-lifter," Daily Star, April 19, 2012, sec. A.

⁶⁷ Hanif M, Mobarak MR, Ronan A, Rahman D, Donovan JJ Jr, Bennish ML, "Fatal renal failure caused by diethylene glycol in paracetamol elixir: the Bangladesh epidemic" *BMJ* 311 6997(1995) 88-91, <http://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC2550149/pdf/bmj00600-0022.pdf>, retrieved on November 10, 2014.

⁶⁸ Emran Hossen, *Justice Delayed, Justice Denied*, the Daily Star, July 22, 2014, Sec. A.

It was alleged that as many as 2000 infants could have died from 1980 to 1990 due to consuming diethylene glycol-laced paracetamol syrup. Following the order of the higher court, the proceeding was halted for the first time in 1994. Then a series of appeals and other delays have stalled the trial over the tragedy. Finally, on the basis of scientific evidence produced by the scientists of Drug Testing Laboratory, the much awaited trial restarted in 2009. On July 22, 2014, the Drug Court sentenced the Adflame Pharmaceuticals managing partner, physician Helena Pasha, his brother and the company's administrative director Mizanur Rahman and production in-charge Nrigendranath Bala to 10 years' imprisonment each for violating section 16 (C) of The Drugs (Control) Ordinance, 1982 by manufacturing adulterated medicines. This is the first court verdict, in the history of Bangladesh, convicting any drug manufacturers of adulterating life saving drugs. However, the proceedings against other companies are still pending due to stay order of the Supreme Court.

Findings and Recommendations

The aforesaid discussions and case studies made it conspicuous that the dream of speedy and fair trials by an independent and impartial judicial mechanism as contemplated by the Constitution will never be materialised keeping the scientific and physical evidence aside, the maximum utilisation of which can only be ensured through a comprehensive legal framework.

- i. A comprehensive legal framework will have to be introduced either by enactment of new law or bringing about necessary amendments in the existing laws. The Draft Evidence (Amendment) Ordinance, 2007 should be placed before the parliament to make it law. The Government has prepared draft of this law with the assistance of the UNDP and Government of Denmark respectively.
- ii. One of the main obstacles, as the earlier discussion reveals, is the procedural problem to depose scientific and physical evidence to courts. Besides some exceptions, the concerned forensic expert is to appear before the court to be undergone examinations like an ordinary witness. Such practice discourages the experts to be involved in the

process of preparing forensic report by collecting and comparing samples. Moreover, taking benefit of adversarial system, the lawyers poses irrelevant questions to the experts causing unexpected delay in the proceedings.

- iii. The sole responsibility to investigate into criminal matters lies in police. According to law, they have to investigate an unnatural, violent and suspicious death to prepare inquest report and even the investigation officer is to decide whether the body should be referred to civil surgeon for medical examination.⁶⁹ But the reality is that most of the police officers do not have sufficient expertise as to how the different injuries present on the body including different changes developed after death will have to be described.⁷⁰ To overcome this problem, coroner system or medical examination system should be introduced.
- iv. Like criminal laws, civil laws are not enforced by police in our country and a separate agency is yet to be created to assist the court to carry out forensic investigation. Therefore, the courts get the job done by different agencies of the state at the expense of the parties that prolongs the procedure.
- v. Various laws dealing with forensic evidence are to be adjusted to create uniformity. For instance, the definition of document as provided in various laws including the Evidence Act has been amended by section 87 of the Information and Communication Technology Act but those laws are yet to be adjusted accordingly.
- vi. There should be coordination among police, judges, magistrates, lawyers and forensic experts to ensure a high standard of medico-legal investigation. To this end, there should be a provision of six months intensive training for newly recruited police officers, judges and lawyers to be enrolled in Bangladesh Bar Council.
- vii. Curricula of our law schools are not designed in interdisciplinary approach. Studying forensic science is almost unknown to our legal education as very few public and

⁶⁹ The Code of Criminal Procedure, 1898, S. 174(3).

⁷⁰ Kamrul Hasan, "Police does not understand language of autopsy," Daily Prothom-alo, April 20, 2012, sec. D

private universities offering undergraduate and graduate programmes in law include this subject in their curricula.

- viii. Under the KOICA project, a modern cyber crime investigation center for cyber crime investigation, training and research, equipped with the digital forensic lab, mobile forensic lab, cyber crime investigation lab, and evidence archive is being established. The FBI donated CODIS software has been established in Forensic Medicine Department of Dhaka Medical College. A legal framework should be made facilitating sufficient number of trained manpower, a regulatory and other logistic supports.
- ix. Sometimes, the courts reject the forensic report as false and fabricated which not only prolongs the trial but also diminishes the possibility of getting justice due damage of the physical evidence. It is because of the fact that the existing law does not provide sufficient guideline as to the collection and preservation of physical evidence.

Conclusion

Justice should not merely be done but it must be seen to be done. However, the poor success in criminal prosecution as well as procrastination in civil litigation does in no sense accord to this norm. When in 21st century, the scientific experts have pushed the frontiers of scientific thinking in favour of the plaintiffs or defendants showing, for instance, that a pharmaceutical product or medical device resulted in a particular injury to the plaintiff, failure of the judicial mechanism to ensure justice for the want of proof not only deprives the justice seeker of his access to justice but also debases the entire fabric of the society. In the absence of a strong legal framework providing a vigorous institutional basis, the investigation and trial in many cases result in failure paving ways for the criminals to escape punishment which will consequently increase crimes in the society. Similarly, maintaining “the balance of probability” in civil litigation with a less concentration on scientific evidence will just prolong the procedure. Therefore, it is emergent for the sake of justice that legislative and administrative initiatives be adopted to form an efficient and strong investigation and judicial mechanism comprising the experts of different disciplines and providing it with modern

equipments and necessary logistic supports. Otherwise utilisation of scientific and forensic evidences in administration of justice will remain a myth in Bangladesh.

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